

Workshop - What Really Drives Students to Learn? A Lean Coffee Discussion

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Abstract

How can we promote greater engagement and motivation among engineering students? Despite the increasing implementation of active learning strategies, many educators still face challenges in maintaining students' enthusiasm, autonomy and sustained interest. This interactive workshop invites participants to reflect collaboratively on these questions using the Lean Coffee format - an agile, participant-driven discussion method that allows groups to self-organise around shared concerns and priorities. Instead of following a fixed agenda, participants will co-create the flow of the session by proposing, voting on and discussing topics related to student engagement and motivation in engineering education. This open structure promotes a more inclusive and reactive environment where diverse experiences and ideas can emerge. By the end of the workshop, participants will have exchanged practical strategies, identified common challenges and jointly developed ideas for improving teaching practices and institutional support systems. The session aims not only to share knowledge, but also to inspire ongoing dialogue and action in the participants' local contexts.

Keywords: Student Engagement; Engineering Education, Lean Coffee.

1 Introduction

Student engagement and motivation strongly influence the learning effectiveness as well as the general effectiveness of education systems. Student engagement and motivation in engineering are widely discussed topics in academic literature. A simple search in the Scopus database using the query ("student engagement" OR "student motivation") AND engineering) yields 5,144 published articles, in a search within Article title, Abstract, and Keywords. This number of articles highlights the significance of this research area.

Some work has been done on how to measuring student engagement, specially through surveys (Maskell & Collins, 2017) (Naibert & Barbera, 2022), as well on how to measuring student motivation (Hauze & Marshall, 2020) (Becerra & Almendra, 2020). In many of those articles the authors provide evidences that the motivation or engagement of students was the result of using some kind of innovation in teaching, specially through active learning approaches (Hernández-de-Menéndez et al., 2019). Examples are through the introduction of gamification (Figueiredo & Garcia-Penalvo, 2020), or in the use of Problem or Project Based Learning (Montero & Gonzalez, 2009) (Alves et al., 2016), or by the use of Flipped Classroom (Lucke & Christie, 2016), or Inquiry-Based Learning (Corral-Barraza et al., 2024).

Although extensive research has been published in books, journals, and conference proceedings, the complexity of the subject highlights the need for further exploration, knowledge generation, and experimentation. To address this gap, this workshop will facilitate dynamic discussions in a Lean Coffee format, bringing together academics to exchange insights and advance the field.

Lean Coffee is a structured, participant-oriented discussion format in which participants collaboratively set the agenda, prioritise topics and engage in time-limited conversations. Unlike traditional meetings with fixed agendas, Lean Coffee allows the group to focus on the most relevant and interesting topics in real time, ensuring a productive and democratic dialogue. Developed in 2010 by organizational consultants Benson and

Lightsmith, this approach applies Lean thinking principles to collaborative discourse, emphasizing value creation through the elimination of procedural waste. The methodology operates through an iterative process wherein participants first generate and prioritize discussion topics democratically, followed by timed conversational intervals that may be extended through collective agreement. This format ensures substantive dialogue while maintaining equitable participation opportunities. Originally conceived within Agile software development communities, the technique has gained broader scholarly and professional adoption due to its demonstrated efficacy in fostering engaged, productive discussions across educational, corporate, and research contexts. The approach's academic significance lies in its empirical validation of emergent agenda-setting as an effective alternative to predetermined meeting structures, particularly in contexts requiring collaborative knowledge construction.

2 Activities

Preparation (10 minutes). Participants will be invited to sit around one or more tables to promote equal participation (as shown in Figure 1). Sticky notes will be delivered for generating topics, as well as a timer to manage the discussions. Briefly explain will be give about the format of Lean Coffee, emphasizing that the agenda will be crowd-sourced and time-bound. The necessary ground rules will be established, such as respecting speaking time and encouraging active listening.

Figure 1. Lean Coffee look.

Topic Generation and Prioritization (15 minutes): Participants will be invited to write down proposals of discussion topics - one per sticky note - and briefly describe each one to the group. All suggestions will be collected and displayed in a board next to the table. Then, a dot-voting process will be conducted: Each participant will have 4 votes (using dots on the sticky notes) to prioritize the most relevant topics. The sticky notes will then be placed in order of votes, creating the discussion agenda.

Time-Boxed Discussions (7 Minutes per Topic): Start with the highest-priority topic and the timer will be set to 7 minutes. The conversation will proceed organically, with participants sharing insights, questions, and perspectives. When the timer ends, the group will decide whether to extend the discussion (by another few minutes) or move to the next topic. This ensures that no single topic dominates the session unless there is strong collective interest.

Closing and Reflection (5–10 minutes): Once all prioritized topics have been addressed or time runs out, conclude with a brief reflection. Ask participants to share key takeaways or feedback on the process. This step helps reinforce learning and provides insights for improving future sessions. Optionally, document action items or unresolved questions for follow-up discussions.

3 Expected results

One of the main expected outcomes is a prioritised list of student engagement and motivation issues that participants believe are most important to address. These might include topics such as the impact of curriculum design on engagement and motivation, the role of real-world projects, the influence of teaching styles or the availability of support resources. Through time-limited discussions, participants can delve into each topic in a targeted way, allowing for meaningful dialogue without the meeting being dominated by a single question or voice.

Another important result is the emergence of actionable ideas. Participants are likely to identify practical measures to improve engagement, such as implementing more project-based learning, setting up peer mentoring programmes or increasing opportunities for students to participate in course design. These suggestions can be documented and used to inform programme improvements or future initiatives. The workshop can also help reveal common frustrations or systemic barriers, laying the groundwork for long-term strategies to improve the academic experience.

Finally, the session is expected to foster stronger communication and a sense of shared responsibility among participants. By taking part in a format that values all voices equally, participants empathise with each other's perspectives and contribute to a better understanding of the academic experience.

4 Conclusions

At the end of this workshop, participants will certainly have experienced an interesting and collaborative exchange of ideas, centred on one of the most present challenges in engineering teaching/learning: how to effectively motivate and involve students. Through the Lean Coffee format, participants will not only share their concerns and classroom realities, but also identify concrete strategies and approaches and opportunities for change. The open and participatory nature of the session allows educators to draw on their own experiences while learning from others, creating a sense of community and shared purpose. Ultimately, this workshop aims to trigger new understandings on the subject and inspire practical innovations to the context that can increase student motivation and learning in various engineering programmes.

References

- Alves, A. C., Sousa, R. M., Fernandes, S., Cardoso, E., Carvalho, M. A., Figueiredo, J., & Pereira, R. M. S. (2016). Teacher's experiences in PBL: implications for practice. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 41(2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2015.1023782>
- Becerra, B. L. G., & Almendra, M. P. R. (2020). Measuring student motivation in a statistics course supported by podcast using Reduced Instructional Materials Motivation Survey (RIMMS). *Proceedings - 10th International Conference on Virtual Campus, JICV 2020*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JICV51605.2020.9375823>
- Corral-Barraza, L., Gómez-Elizalde, J., Morán-Soto, G., Godínez-García, F., & González Peña, O. (2024). Transforming Electronics Engineering Classrooms: Fostering Students' Motivation to Design Technological Solutions Through Inquiry-Based Learning. *IEEE Access*, 4–63. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3413011>
- Figueiredo, J., & García-Penalvo, F. J. (2020). Increasing student motivation in computer programming with gamification. *IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference, EDUCON, 2020-April*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/EDUCON45650.2020.9125283>
- Hauze, S., & Marshall, J. (2020). Validation of the Instructional Materials Motivation Survey: Measuring Student Motivation to Learn via Mixed Reality Nursing Education Simulation. *International Journal on E-Learning: Corporate, Government, Healthcare, and Higher Education*, 19(1).
- Hernández-de-Menéndez, M., Vallejo Guevara, A., Tudón Martínez, J. C., Hernández Alcántara, D., & Morales-Menendez, R. (2019). Active learning in engineering education. A review of fundamentals, best practices and experiences. *International Journal on Interactive Design and Manufacturing*, 13(3). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12008-019-00557-8>
- Lucke, T., & Christie, M. F. (2016). Using the flipped classroom approach in engineering courses to improve student motivation and learning outcomes. *International Symposium on Project Approaches in Engineering Education*, 6.

- Maskell, E. C., & Collins, L. (2017). Measuring student engagement in UK higher education: do surveys deliver? In *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education* (Vol. 9, Issue 2). <https://doi.org/10.1108/JARHE-11-2015-0082>
- Montero, E., & Gonzalez, M. J. (2009). Student engagement in a structured problem-based approach to learning: A first-year electronic engineering study module on heat transfer. *IEEE Transactions on Education*, 52(2). <https://doi.org/10.1109/TE.2008.924219>
- Naibert, N., & Barbera, J. (2022). Development and Evaluation of a Survey to Measure Student Engagement at the Activity Level in General Chemistry. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 99(3). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jchemed.1c01145>